

THE LUMINOUS ETHER

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Abstract: This essay presented here discusses the theory about the luminous ether from two points of view - the physical on the one hand - and - the esoteric on the other. In the physical aspect, we present the point of view of Einstein (1920) and Huygens (1602). In the metaphysical aspect, we address the general view of mystics or occultists. The central idea of this essay is: how the luminescence of the luminous ether impregnates and/or is imprinted on ethereal matter (?). Our method is phenomenological. And our objective is to delve a little deeper into the enigmatic nature of the luminous ether, which, for many, its origin and functioning is still unknown.

Keywords: Luminous ether. Luminescence. Metaphysics.

The etheric particle: an introduction

I begin this essay with a quote from Albert Einstein (1920, emphasis mine), he says: “according to the general theory of relativity, *space without ether is unthinkable*; because, in such a space, *not only would there be no propagation of light, but also no possibility of existence for patterns of space and time* (measuring sticks and clocks), nor, therefore, space-time intervals in the physical sense.” I begin by saying that the ether, itself, emerged as an absolute and veridical scientific reality only from the 19th century onwards through, mainly, two fantastic minds, namely Isaac Newton and Albert Einstein. It was only through experiments in laboratories and in the free air that the real existence of a substance “different” from other substances was reliably proven, a type of special matter not seen or even perceived physically; something like coming from the heavenly coverings and/or fields or, in the words of many physicists, a creation and at the same time a mystery of God.

In this sense, the ether was and still is a great mystery and, on the other hand, a great discovery of science, even though its origin is unknown. The universe pulsates in the unfathomable immensity of infinity and this “strange particle” participates in the entire vibratory process of all movements of life within the Earth, that is, terrestrial, or even outside, extraterrestrial. According to Douglas Gabriel (2017) in *The Eternal Ether*, the ether, above all, of the human organism, has an intrinsic relationship with *the movement or rotation of the planets*, mainly, of the stars, among the

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main ones, are Jupiter, the Moon, the Sun and even the Earth. According to him, during daylight, the Sun's luminosity has an immanent and absolute relationship with our *mental body* and, during the night, in the darkness of the nocturnal moment, the Moon has a powerful and deep relationship with our *bloodstream*.

He means that it is as if, in the clarity of day, the luminescence of the solar luminous rays not only illuminates external matter, but, above all, it is as if the powerful light of the sun (which is mostly immaterial) comes into connection and in tune with the ether of physical (and psychic) space, vibrating, through the medium (material and immaterial), the etheric particles of the internal part of our mental space (physical and transcendental consciousness). On the other hand, in physical terms, according to Einstein, "space without the ether is unthinkable". But why? In mystical and metaphysical terms, the space we know, *this external* that we inhabit and at the same time inhabits us has a "mind" similar to ours (perspective of panpsychism), and the existence of this "mind" only becomes possible when the energy of the ether enters or, in its embodied state, passes into *incorporate* the space. In metaphorical terms, it would be like this - the human mind works organically only with the vibration and connection of the synthesis of neurons, while the "mind of space" exists and vibrates only because, within its immaterial interior, vibrate and experience the *ether particles*.

According to an esoteric position, *the ideas of the Universal Mind are imprinted on matter*. And this is only possible thanks to the ether particles in the universe that, in addition to *give body* or providing the necessary materiality for these ideas to be infused, turns, above all, matter from an inactive, passive and, par excellence, inert construct into an active, living and self-moving organism. Firstly, the ideas of this Mind are properly and by nature "ideas" mainly because of the luminescence of the luminous corpuscles (the light) contained and inseparably connected with the etheric particles. The ether is not "ether" without light, just as light would not be "light" without the ether.

The so-called modern science, despite the great advances, is still a long way from witnessing and proving what would actually exist in the *interval* between these two "substances" - the "ether" and "light". It is very difficult for science to prove this or even discover what "is" there simply because such "organisms" are and are alive throughout our atmosphere and not just that; they, as they move, they *I will mold* to any type of surface, material or immaterial. It turns out that our science unfortunately does not yet have the capacity to discover things created in *immaterial medium*, because, in the materialist conception of science, to prove that something exists it is essential to "see", "touch", "experience" and not just "perceive", "feel", etc.

Then we have a question: "how to think about 'space'"? What would "space" really be? Well, in our view, man has made this space too complex by describing and characterizing it with an

infinite number of characters - “physical space”; “mental space”; “cosmic space”; “space of consciousness”; “outer space”; “structural space”; “expansive space”, “lived space”, “transcendent space”, etc., all to demonstrate the various faces of this category of analysis. But, let's think about it - “is space really ontologically a ‘category’ or is it just a ‘space’, that is, a *single space, the same* for everyone”? We are convinced that space is one simply because the substance of ether or light is also one.

Physicists even speak of a “ether light” to say that space could not exist without light or ether. In other words, space as we know it, whatever type it may be, is not exactly space because such “space” can only be configured as “space” with light and ether. And even in the dark of day, in every shadow *coexists* a light and in all light the ether. In short, we can say this - “even before the existence and appearance of all matter, there is, in a primordial way, *the absolute of space* when “light” and “ether” are its main “living organisms”. Therefore, only later, with space *inside* from space, matter is infused into its fabric again also by the luminescence of the light of the ether.

In terms of measurement, after much reading about the meaning *space-time*, even today, for scholars, it is very difficult to try to measure on a scale which of the two - space or time - would be the most abstract and complex “entity” possible. Because they are both *absolute*, therefore, they have a firmly “absolute” existence. On the other hand, even in the curious emptiness of space or the strange absolute universe of time, the ether would be in a *much deeper than both* because, again, both space and time are like this, in this way, because within both light and ether vibrate. As Einstein himself stated above - “without the ether there would be no sense of space-time”. According to him, “to deny the ether one must ultimately assume that the *empty space* it has physical qualities.” In other words, within space in its original or primordial form there would in fact be the vibration of informatively “physical” particles when forming and shaping what we know as the “fabric of space”.

It turns out that the created things, that is, the divine things, of God, were made in a way that, in most cases, only He could tell us or decipher this enigma of life. In my main book, *Tratado de Psicometafísica*², in the chapter “Consciousness and Cosmos”, I deal with this subject by saying, based on esoteric philosophy, that “the world-with-form was created from the world-without-form”. In other words, in transcendental terms, all divine creation has as its primordial source of existence the *Absolute*, which would be the *Unknowable*, the *Uno* or the *Pure Act*. In this way and for this reason, the majority of existing things are absolutely “immaterial”, therefore, every indication of matter originated from a thing *immaterial*. Do you see, then, how far science, even modern, is from great discoveries about ours and all of creation?

² SANTOS, C. *Psychometaphysics Treatise*. Pará de Minas: VirtualBooks, 2024.

Albert Einstein was, without a doubt, a great intellectual man and he, along with Newton, were figures at the forefront of their time because, with regard to the ether, they managed to state in a well-founded way *the existence ipso facto* of the ether in the universe. And it was, based on its science, that the esoteric school began to create conjectures around the genesis and functioning of the ether in cosmic space. Newton, then, would have founded a theory for “absolute space” which, in letters, Einstein says that: “Newton’s absolute space would be the ether”. It is seen, then, that the absolute of not only space, but of every vital element (and even amorphous or inorganic) is *permeated* by the force of etheric energy. That is, all *quite* presents itself as a given and immediate “phenomenon” thanks to the vitality and vivacity of the ether. Thus, for science, the ether would be a “particle” or a “substance”, but, in fact, according to Douglas Gabriel (2017), the ether would be the “theory of everything”.

Descartes, for example, was an intellectual physicist and metaphysician when his intellect spread and is still disseminated today in all intellectual structures of the theory of knowledge. And of course, Descartes, would not achieve this without building a memory about his ancestors, that is, all the physics and metaphysics of his predecessors. In this sense, for Descartes, “the ether is omnipresent”. Therefore, it was Newton and Einstein who used this statement to create and discover, through experiments, the “absolute living presence of the ether in the universe”. Following a mystical tradition, the ether would not only be “omnipresent”, but “omniscient” because it (the ether) would be contained in every surface, abstract or concrete and even in that which does not yet have a name. Ether would be “Life”, alive or not, organic or inorganic. For example, scientific theory has not yet discovered what goes on in the deep abstract interiority of a being or inorganic matter, as it only knows that there is ether there, but it does not know what is found there in the deep, internal part. of this phenomenon.

For us, and I think for every scientist as well, the universe as a small part of it we know is so complex, so deep and abysmal that, to be honest and humble scientists, we must “hang our heads” or retreat from the masterful and, perhaps, indecipherable Creation. In other words, man wanted to reach the Moon and he did; He wanted to reach Mars and got closer, but his ambition is so great that he doesn't realize that the universe created by a God is, in its immense totality, an immaterial and invisible universe. Even Buddhists, after much prayer and meditation, say that at the edge of the Earth where we are here, all this is just a mere *image* or *reflection*. In a word, “illusion”!

Perhaps this is why the best or most appropriate path for a scientist or visionary is the perception or science of first beginning their scientific discovery with a *unique phenomenon* as *the luminous state imprinted on matter* of, for example, a measly insect or an “inorganic” matter such as a candle. It was discovered that “there” there is a profound synthesis of atoms and ethers, but, perhaps, what science has not discovered is - “how this relationship between atom, ether and empty

space comes to be *coexist* harmoniously? Thus, the question is not why science is “materialist”, but the fundamental thing is that these things created in the material environment have as their primordial source *the invisibility of its own phenomenon*, that is, the abstract thought of its important and essential “immateriality”.

According to an important physicist from the Middle Ages to the modern age called Christian Huygens (1660) - “one can conceive that these particles of ether, despite their small size, are still composed of other parts, and their elasticity consists in the very rapid movement of a subtle matter, which crosses them on all sides, and forces their structure to be arranged in such a way as to provide this fluid with the most open and easy passage possible.” According to Huygens, there are also other types of particles in the ether particles that, according to him, are perhaps responsible for making the ether a subtle matter and, therefore, fluid, possibly originating from “another dimension”. As Aristotle once said something like this - “I suggest that the ether is a *quintessence* originating from the celestial environment, also found, in a primordial and essential way, in the stars of the universe.

As Huygens (1660) himself states, ether particles are everywhere and their character of *elasticity* or *viscosity* makes it a special particle that *goes through everything*, in a dead or alive state. In our view, this thought would not be a “great discovery”, after all, the ether, being of a totally immaterial nature, can permeate every present or absent substance, every physical or extraphysical form, every visible or non-visible contour, in short, every point, corner, shape or measure, abstract or not. And there would be the fundamental part of our essay - “how the ether (in its luminous state) penetrates matter *printing* in it all his ‘being’”?

We will deal with this in the next topic.

2. Phenomenologization of the luminescence of luminous corpuscles imprinted on matter by the etheric fluid

We begin this fundamental topic with a beautiful quote from Huygens (1660, emphasis mine), when he says - “the luminous ether *penetrates the substance of every material body* with little or no resistance, as free perhaps as the wind *pass* through a grove of trees.” Huygens' observation through physical experiments only further proves the thought of esotericism that says that the ether propagates or is contained in the four elements of life - “fire”, “air”, “earth”, and “water”. Far ahead of science, esoteric philosophy asserts that etheric particles are “fiery” because they are “electric and magnetic”; they are “spatial” because they cross the entire body; They are “terrestrial” because they are contained in every vital element of the Earth and they are “fluid or

aqueous” because it is like “water” that dissolves and transforms all matter. It turns out that, for our objective and to try to better detail this “force” of the ether in a phenomenal way, we will glimpse a particular phenomenon, namely, “how the luminous ether penetrates and, upon penetrating, imprints on matter the organic part of life ” (?).

According to Huygens (1660): “no person has yet been found to have explained in a probable way these first and most notable phenomena of light, namely: why it only propagates following straight lines and like visual rays, coming from an infinite number of places, *cross paths without getting in each other's way*”. It can be seen how far science is again from proving a series of physical phenomena in the universe, among them, *those of light*. For example, how light, the one we know, that is, an ordinary light like the “light from a lamp” manages, with its little structural organicity (as a lamp does not have great luminous qualities like a street lamp), to bypass the entire middle limit as a quarter? It was then discovered that it propagates in straight lines; which demonstrates the power of synthesis of all its luminous corpuscles throughout the physical environment as they transform into symmetrical or linear forms of forces. The *luminous cohesion* it is intensely and dizzyingly absolute when, in the contact of the vibration of its particles, that is, in the synthesis and vibration of the atoms together with the ethers, *lighten large portions of space* and, in detail, all at once, in the absolute immediacy of the phenomenon. Like, for example, also, *the burning flame of a candle*. Let us now dwell on this phenomenon.

The moment the candle is lit, the contour around it is illuminated as it also, in an absolutely dark environment, illuminates on a dizzying scale other environments (or other spaces) such as the portions of space distant from the origin of the luminosity. In this case, it seems that the burning flame while burning makes the ether particles of the fire of space “burn”, as well as that of the flame itself and, between them, there would be a “fiery tune” (esoteric sense). It is curious to realize that the existence of the ether has already been scientifically proven, but, on the other hand, it happens that in this example of the candle flame lit in an absolutely dark environment like a room, the “being” called “ether” at the same time *immaterially inform the space*, making it like a “fabric”, loose and dynamic, connecting, in an absolute way, with the burning etheric spatiality of the candle flame, when everything in this phenomenon, that is, the whole process happens in an absolutely *immediate*, as in the infinitesimal speed at the moment a “light” is turned on. It also happens that it is incredible to notice in this phenomenon, the splendor *harmony* with which everything happens because, as soon as the candle carries the “flame”, it seems that the entire circular and linear space is *filled in at once*, that is, at the same time, by the luminescence of its luminous corpuscle (the candle flame).

At the same time that the flame time crystal lights up, the entire spatial organism is also lit, also imprinting, on all circular matter, the *clues* of the flame that still burns again. The phenomenon

becomes even more complex when the substance that is “air” intensifies the extraordinary luminosity. And even more, in the immanence of more darkness, in an even “magical” way, the luminescence of the flame becomes *amplify*. Without the flame, the candle is an inert medium. On the other hand, in the absoluteness of the candle's act of “feeling” the flame, its “being” that was “inorganic” or “inanimate” reawakens from its “latent” state. Yes, the candle “waits” to be burned, just as a “conscience” waits for something to happen. As a material entity that it is, it “waits” for another entity (in this case, a human) to awaken the *what for* the candle exists. In short, a candle only exists with its flame and it only becomes a “semi-conscious” being in the living presence because it is illuminated by the flame. Well, even a simple candle begins to “suffer”, slowly, *the succumbing of its way of existence*.

In this case, not only the “light of the ether”, but also the “ether of light” becomes *print* in the matter of space the absolute content of the existence of its vivacity. Thus, the organic fluid from the “burning” of the candle becomes *dissolve* in the fluid of space fire when, in fact, it would be the “burning flame” that was the fundamental cause of the “awakening of space fire”. In this sense, everyone is called upon to *revive* causing, in the fabric of space, the “waking up” of etheric particles of space fire. Thus, space can only “shine” from a first cause or an executed act, otherwise, space is just empty or a latent silence.

According to physics, in luminescence, atoms *absorb part of the energy* coming from some external source, *reissued-a* in the form of visible light. In the particular case of the luminescence of the candle flame, the apparent light becomes a visible phenomenon thanks to all the energy (which was in a latent state) distributed throughout the circumspection of physical space and, above all, around the candle. Thus, empty space is not composed of “atoms”, but of another type of particles, among them, only one known - the “ether”. In this sense, the latent energy of the ethers of empty space awakens with the synthesis of atoms inside the candle when its luminescence reaches other possible spatial contours at one time or another. Light being light and in becoming light, its luminous atoms have already absorbed a good part of its external energy, which, in this case, we still do not know how to infer what its source would be. In any case, in all the condensed energy *coexists, at the same time*, the condensation of atoms, as energy alone would not be able to spread throughout the environment without the harmonious synthesis of atoms.

Physics also states that the conservation of a *momentum* produces energy conservation. In other words, at each moment there is contained a part or portion of energy that was distributed a moment ago. In this case, it would be like *act* and *potency* in the Thomistic sense. That is, the energy of the previous moment *preserves* the energy of the subsequent moment. And, in an abstraction of this phenomenon, the person who would do this would be the “being of time”. A given luminous medium retains the energy of the appearance of a previous luminous medium;

which means that the candle flame *feedback* of each action or each act of each its own focus of luminosity. That is why the candle flame, as one suffers the luminous effects of its existence, *expanding* in an infinitesimal way the remnants of the luminosity focus of a previous space of time and *progressing* in the way of illuminating the next portions of space. This position of ours is consistent with Huygens' thought when he says - "the waves of light propagate in the ethereal matter that continuously occupies *the interstices or pores* of transparent bodies. For as it passes through them continually and with ease, it follows that they are always filled with it."

Thus, in this sense, the luminous corpuscle of the candle continually and constantly fills all the space that was empty in the sense that the darkness of its emptiness is *intensely* outlined by its luminescence. An issue with this phenomenon that has not yet been addressed by physics are precisely these "interstices or pores" where the energy flows of the atom and ether in light meet and dissociate. And this deserves more attention.

According to Huygens (1960), ethereal matter and its force occupies the *interstices* or the *couples* of the entire transparent body. In this sense, for him, all etheric force would be contained in the interstice or "interval" of all matter, in this case, reflective or translucent (transparent). Thus, the formal matter of a transparent thing like glass has its reflection as its origin in *intersection* of its own material form. In other words, as light does not propagate without the ether (Einstein), the corpuscles of its luminous rays acquire "force" (supernatural) through a spatial form *at intersection*, that is, precisely in the *interval* between the propagation of light and the transparent medium. We could say that despite advances in science, it would be a long way from, for example, witnessing phenomena like this at a time when scientists have not yet discovered what happens, experimentally, inside this so-called "interstice". Perhaps, it would be necessary to base ourselves on an "ontology of the propagation of light".

In order to prove that ethereal matter *penetrates* the entire material body, Huygens (1960), through experiments, states - "when light passes through a hollow glass sphere, closed on all sides, it is *full* of ethereal matter, such as the spaces outside the sphere. As was shown before, this ethereal matter consists of particles that practically touch each other." If we can talk like this, the universe *sensorial* of ethereal matter is absolutely open, expansive and dynamic, as it is as if this special type of matter (which is not really "matter") were *all invisible form of any material body* or, in a word, the inner part of your *soul*. She would be neither the light nor the shadow, but her *interstice*; which means that ethereal matter is as if it were a material fluid, but immaterial (that is, despite being invisible, organic) that passes through the entire environment, projecting into the pores of any surface as, at the same time, *print* in all matter external to you a subtle energy not yet completely known.

Given this, it seems to us that the created world really arose from a *Primordial Light*. However, it turns out that such “Light” would not be a possible existing body without containing the ether as physics today demonstrates and proves. Perhaps, and this mystics are in agreement, the ether would be a much more primary substance than light itself because such “ether” would have been contained since a time when *nothing existed*, only darkness and cloudiness (the *Bottomless Abyss* in Stein (1994) and Santos (2023)). Thus, “ether” is synonymous with “cosmic”, that is, when everything was just “darkness”, an eternal Nothingness, however, the Cosmos already existed, being, in the sense of Santos (2024), the first thing created by God.

In order to illustrate the mystery that the ether is still for us, the Spirit André Luiz, psychographed by Chico Xavier tells us the following: “we know that light moves in corpuscular beams that we call 'photons', we are not unaware that the atom is a whirlpool of positive and negative forces, whose potentials vary with the number of electrons or force particles around the nucleus, informing us that energy, when condensed, appears as mass to later transform into energy ; however, the subtle way in which atomic systems oscillate cannot be equated with our knowledge. Until now we have named this ‘indefinable terrain’ as the ether; informing, additionally, that “matter is also a condensation of energy””. In other words, the entire medium is composed of “luminous corpuscular beams” or “photons” caused by the intensive vibration and synthesis of the positive and negative poles of the atoms (the electrons), finding the imperious and supernatural force in the *intervals* of corpuscular encounters (the ether). In this way, what we today call “subtle matter” would be nothing more than “that thing, at the moment indecipherable, that exists in the *corpuscular coexistence of things*, or rather, that “being” that inhabits the “interval” and “feeds back” on the impulse of the vibration of the atoms throughout the corpuscular medium. In this sense, in our view, a deeper understanding of a corpuscular theory of “light” in an etheric medium would be important to better clarify this supposed “corpuscular intersection”.

Following this same spiritist line, Allan Kardec ([1857] (2021)) in *Book of Spirits* says: “God, as Supreme Intelligence, primary cause of all things, Spirit, as Intelligent Being, and matter are the principle of everything that exists, with matter (coagulated light) being a transitory stage of the universal cosmic fluid/ ether”. In this sense, for both spiritists and occultists, the “coagulated light” would be precisely that “interval or interstice” where the ethereal force is actually “contained”, in the sense that the light, in its transitory state of vibration, remains, for an infinitesimal interval of time, “stagnant”. Of course, this supernatural state cannot be seen with the eyes of the body, only in a heightened consciousness, with the eyes of the spirit.

At a certain moment, when the light “coagulates”, possibly this means that it is being absolutely filled, at the same time, with the necessary energy of both the atom and the ether to actually become, in a living presence, a corpuscular form of light . Then, it is as if the light, for a

moment, interrupted its luminous vibratory flow in order to be filled with more energy (atomic and etheric), providing propulsion to remain “illuminating” in the otherwise empty space. There is no such thing as an absolutely “dark” environment because physics itself has proven that even “black holes” have, inside them, *luminosity*. It is clear that the light *penetrates* really any body in the emptiness of space in the sense that the “vacuum” itself is also luminosity. In fact, as perceptive beings that we are, how could we perceive all things in the world without daylight (the Sun) or even nightlight (the Moon)?

According to the first law of thermodynamics, *energy can neither be created nor destroyed, but can only be converted from one form to another*. In this sense, in the corpuscular theory of light, all light energy can only be *converted* perfectly through *intervals* from the pores of the ether particles imprinted beforehand throughout the luminous corpuscle. This statement means that nothing will be created again, nor will it even be destroyed, but everything will be *transformed*. Physics says: “nothing is created because everything is *renew*”. It is in this sense that ethereal matter in the form of “coagulated light” does not start to create anything, nor does it destroy to create again; just *transform* that energy contained or condensed in new germs of corpuscles of light.

God, in His Perfection, created, that is, imposed His first act, which was pure par excellence. Thus, from God's first act (his finger or hand), the other acts began to preserve this first act or first cause, giving rise to what we know today as: the “created universe”. In this way, the energy of the first act was conserved by the second (its reflection image) and, from this second, *disseminated* in the others, finally giving the origin of the Form of the World, that is, the infinite set of created things.

In this sense, we agree with Allan Kardec when he told us that: “there is an ethereal fluid that *fill* space and *penetrates* the bodies. *This fluid* is the ether or primitive cosmic matter, generator of the world and beings”. A primordial “fluid” such as “blood” is for our organism. A type of fluid that *in transit* the entire fabric of universal forms and, during the interval of their passage, render such forms with an “organic” aspect, in a word, “alive”.

Thus, the entire luminous corpuscle “vibrates”, that is, “shines”, not only because “light” is a vibratory process, but the thing to understand is that, within this vibration, *vibrates* also ethereal matter. With this, the light spreads even as a “supersensitive organ and/or organism” to the point of crossing the beyond limit of all matter.

A curious note: not only meditation, but, above all, prayer communicates to us about things like this *transcend* the limit of our intellect. The *prayer*, therefore, makes us see the wonders of created things, freeing us from the prisons of matter and all the nebulosity that it entails, and, above all, calling us to witness the *life of the spirit*.

Finally, perhaps, with this brief synthesis about the ether, in this case, luminous, we could say (without stating) that it is indeed a type of *spirit*. Therefore, in a future time, it will not be science that will bring the truth, it will be spirituality that will better reveal to us the enigmatic nature of this “subtle matter”.

Final considerations

In order to conclude our essay briefly and without solutions on the future of the discovery of the ether (as Einstein rightly says), I ask permission to conclude with a quote from Emmanuel psychographed by Chico Xavier, he tells us - “men have of matter (universal cosmic fluid/ether), the conceptualization possible to be provided by your mind, understanding that the real aspect of the world is not one that mortal eyes can encompass. The time will come when science will understand that the Universe and, by extension, all celestial bodies, all organic and inorganic beings are *ether frequencies*, including our physical bodies.”

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